

A STUDY ON THE PERCEPTION OF GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (GHRM) PRACTICES

Sourav Basu

Assistant Professor, Norbuling Rigter College (Affiliated to Royal University of Bhutan) Paro, Bhutan

ARTICLE INFO.

Keywords: Environmentally, Green Products, Employee Engagement, Organizational Performance.

Abstract

GHRM practices can encompass a range of initiatives, including employee training on sustainable practices, environmentally friendly workplace policies, and the development of green products or services. These practices are crucial in today's business world, where environmental sustainability is becoming increasingly important for organizations to remain competitive. One of the primary goals of GHRM is to increase employee engagement in environmental sustainability practices. In this article the researcher has aimed at examining the perception of Norbuling Rigter College (NRC) staff towards GHRM and to find out the awareness level of NRC staff about the GHRM. For this purpose the Quantitative research with a descriptive approach was used. The survey data were collected using Google form from 46 staff of Norbuling Rigter College, Paro. The questionnaire is adapted from the study of Nath and Goel (2018). Certain modifications are made to the questionnaire to suit the requirements of the study. All questions are Likert scale questions. The study reveals that The NRC staff has a strong inclination towards GHRM practices. The organization has moderately implemented sustainable practices across all dimensions, with the exception of Green Job Design and Encouraging an Employee to Participate in Green Agenda.

<http://www.gospodarkainnowacje.pl/> © 2023 LWAB.

Introduction: The term "green human resource management" (GHRM) is becoming more popular in the HR industry. Green HR practises comprise environmentally friendly HR setup, policies, and procedures for long-term usage of an organization's green culture, resulting in enhanced efficiency, less waste, a better attitude towards one's job, a better quality of life at work, cheaper expenses, and improved employee satisfaction and retention. In order to safeguard the environment, human resource management (GHRM) policies and practises are used. Employees' attitudes towards the environment are helped by GHRM. In order to create an organisation that is environmentally sensitive, resource-efficient, and socially responsible, green human resources management (GHRM) is defined as a set of policies, practises, and systems that support employee behaviour that is environmentally conscious, resource-efficient, and socially responsible. It is commonly known that implementing green practises will save costs and increase revenue for the organisation. To encourage higher efficiency, boost work satisfaction among employees, save costs, and involve staff members in a meaningful way, the GHRM adopts environmentally friendly HR practises. The organization's attempts to raise awareness of

environmental concerns rely heavily on GHRM. It is necessary to create HR policies and procedures, educate employees to be more environmentally sensitive, and put environmental rules into effect. Employees are demonstrating significant positive intentions for increased employee engagement and work satisfaction in those organisations that are putting the "Go Green" idea into practice, according to Yusoff et al. (2015). Practices that support sustainable practices inside the company and encourage staff to adopt environmentally friendly habits define GHRM. The ultimate objective of GHRM is to develop a workplace that is socially and ecologically responsible, promotes employee happiness, and increases productivity.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Sharma (2021) reviewed the literature regarding the perception of GHRM practices. The study findings revealed that GHRM policies improve the confidence level of workers. In addition, the presentation, practices, disposition, and capabilities of HR can be enhanced and enriched through the transformation of GHRM. Environmental knowledge helps in practicing GHRM (Ahmad et al, 2021).

Islam et al. (2019) examined the perception of GHRM practices among managers in the banking industry. The study found that managers had a relatively low level of awareness and understanding of GHRM practices, and that they were skeptical about the potential benefits of such practices.

Krambia-Kapardis et al. (2018) explored the attitudes of employees towards GHRM practices in the hospitality industry. The study found that employees had a positive perception of GHRM practices, and that they believe that such practices could improve both environmental sustainability and organizational performance.

Similarly, a study by Tariq et al. (2018) examined the perception of GHRM practices among employees in the manufacturing sector. The study found that employees had a positive perception of GHRM practices, and that they believed that such practices could improve both environmental sustainability and employee job satisfaction.

Similarly, a study by Khan et al. (2017) examined the perception of GHRM practices among employees in the construction industry. The study found that employees had a low level of awareness and understanding of GHRM practices, and that they were skeptical about the potential benefits of such practices.

Statement of the Problem: By reviewing the different literature on the concept of GHRM practices and their influence on employees' job satisfaction it is inferred that GHRM is a vital component of the organization's growth and development. The organization that has adopted the GHRM practices is successful in terms of the growth and retention of its employees. To the knowledge of the researcher, no constructive study has been made to judge the perceptions of employees regarding GHRM practices. This creates a knowledge gap. This perception study is important because it would help in the effective implementation of the GHRM practices because of its growing significance over time.

Objectives: The present study has been carried out with the following objectives-

To examine the perception of NRC staff towards GHRM.

To find out the awareness level of NRC staff about the GHRM.

Hypothesis: Considering the objectives the researcher has formulated the following objectives-

HO1- The perception of the employees towards the GHRM practices is high.

HO2- There is a statistically significant difference between the age groups in the Overall GHRM perception.

METHODOLOGY:**Research Design**

The study employed Quantitative research with a descriptive approach.

Number of Respondents Participated in the Study

The survey data were collected from 46 respondents.

Study Area

Norbuling Rigter College (NRC), Paro, Bhutan.

Data Collection Procedure: The survey data were collected using Google form.

Development of Questionnaire: The questionnaire is adapted from the study of Nath and Goel (2018). Certain modifications are made to the questionnaire to suit the requirements of the study. All questions are Likert scale questions.

Questionnaire Reliability and Validity: As the survey instrument was adapted from previous studies, content validity was already established. For reliability, checking Cronbach's alpha was calculated. The Cronbach's alpha score was at 0.874 for the 25 items that is considered as quite good and acceptable.

Data Analysis Technique: Software called Excel was used to analyse the data. The study goals will be examined using regression, Anova tests, and perception index.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:**Table 1: Mean Perception of GHRM Practices**

Dimensions	Green Recruitment and Training	Energy Efficient Workspace	Waste Management	Green Job Design	Vehicle Sharing	Encouraging an employee to participate in Green Agenda	Green Reward System
Mean	3.60	3.78	3.71	3.21	3.49	3.13	3.65

This table 1 shows the mean values for different dimensions related to sustainability practices in the workplace. The dimensions are Green Recruitment and Training, Energy Efficient Workspace, Waste Management, Green Job Design, Vehicle Sharing, Encouraging an Employee to Participate in Green Agenda, and Green Reward System. The mean value for Green Recruitment and Training is 3.60, which suggests that on average, the organization has moderately implemented sustainable practices in their recruitment and training processes. The mean value for Energy Efficient Workspace is 3.78, indicating that the organization has implemented sustainable practices to a somewhat higher extent in designing an energy-efficient workspace. The mean value for Waste Management is 3.71, indicating that the organization has moderately implemented sustainable practices for managing waste in the workplace. The mean value for Green Job Design is 3.21, indicating that the organization has implemented sustainable practices to a lesser extent in designing green jobs. The mean value for Vehicle Sharing is 3.49, suggesting that the organization has moderately implemented sustainable practices in terms of encouraging vehicle sharing. The mean value for Encouraging an Employee to Participate in Green Agenda is 3.13, indicating that the organization has implemented sustainable practices to a lesser extent in encouraging employees to participate in green initiatives. The mean value for Green Reward System is 3.65, indicating that the organization has moderately implemented sustainable practices in terms of rewarding employees for engaging in environmentally-friendly practices.

Overall, the means suggest that the organization has moderately implemented sustainable practices

across all dimensions, with the exception of Green Job Design and Encouraging an Employee to Participate in Green Agenda, where the implementation is slightly lower.

Fig. Showing the mean values of different dimensions of GHRM

GHRM Perception Index

A GHRM perception index was developed to understand the perception of the employees towards the GHRM practices. The index is designed by applying the following formulae:

Table 2: GHRM Awareness Index

Sum of actual score of 46 respondents (A)	4400
Sum of the maximum score of 46 respondents (B)	7130
A/B*100	62%

$$\text{GHRM Perception Index} = 4400/7130*100 = 62\%$$

The following steps were followed to determine the awareness level. Firstly, the sums of all the items relating to measuring the financial inclusion scheme awareness were added. Secondly, the maximum score that the respondents can achieve was calculated. Finally, the actual score was divided by the maximum score. The derived result is multiplied by 100 to convert it into a percentage.

Table 2 shows the GHRM perception index. The perception index score of 62% signifies that the staff has a strong inclination towards GHRM practices. Therefore, it is concluded that if the GHRM practices are implemented then it would receive huge applause from the staff.

Table 3: ANOVA

Overall GHRM

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.674	4	.418	2.753	.041
Within Groups	6.233	41	.152		
Total	7.907	45			

The between-groups factor in this table 3 has a Sum of Squares of 1.674, 4 degrees of freedom, and a Mean Square of 0.418. The within-groups factor has a Mean Square of 0.152, a Sum of Squares of 6.233, and 41 degrees of freedom. The overall variation has 45 degrees of freedom and a Sum of Squares of 7.907. The corresponding p-value (Sig.) is 0.041 and the F-statistic is 2.753, which is lower than the standard alpha threshold of 0.05. This suggests that there is a statistically significant variation

in the perception of the overall GHRM between at least two of the age groups.

Findings:

- The organization has moderately implemented sustainable practices across all dimensions, with the exception of Green Job Design and Encouraging an Employee to Participate in Green Agenda.
- The NRC staff has a strong inclination towards GHRM practices.
- There is a statistically significant variation in the perception of the overall GHRM between at least two of the age groups of NRC Staff.

Conclusion: GHRM practices involve various policies and strategies aimed at reducing environmental impacts in organizations. These practices include but are not limited to energy and resource conservation, waste reduction, and recycling, green procurement, eco-friendly transportation, and the adoption of sustainable practices in product design and production. The adoption of GHRM practices also involves the promotion of environmental awareness among employees and the development of a culture of sustainability within the organization.

References:

1. Armstrong, M. (2009). HR policies procedures and systems. *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*, 11th ed., 985-1015.
2. Bebbington, J. (2001). Sustainable development: A review of the international development, business and accounting literature. *Accounting Forum*, 25, 128–157.
3. Berrone, P., & Gomez-Mejia, L. R. (2009). Environmental performance and executive compensation: An integrated agency-institutional perspective. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52(1), 103-126.
4. Deshwal, P. (2015). Green Human Resource Management: An organizational strategy of greening people. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(13), 176-181.
5. Dutta, S. (2012). Greening people: A strategic dimension. *ZENITH: International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research*, 2, 143–148.
6. Haden, S. S. P., Oyler, J. D., & Humphreys, J. H. (2009). Historical, practical, and theoretical perspectives on green management: An exploratory analysis. *Management Decision*, 47(7), 1041-1055.
7. Lin, B., Jones, C. A., & Hsieh, C. T. (2001). Environmental practices and assessment: a process perspective. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*.
8. Lee, K. (2009). Gender differences in Hong Kong adolescent consumers' green purchasing behavior. *Journal of consumer marketing*.
9. Mathapati, C. M. (2013). Green Human Resource Management: A strategic facet. *Tactful Management Research Journal*, 2(2), 1–6.
10. Mehta, K., & Chugan, P. K. (2015). Green HRM in pursuit of environmentally sustainable business. *Pursuit of Environmentally Sustainable Business* (June 1, 2015). *Universal Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 3(3), 74-81.
11. Tranfield, D., Denyer, D., & Smart, P. (2003). Towards a methodology for developing evidence-informed management knowledge by means of systematic review. *British journal of management*, 14(3), 207-222.
12. Zoogah, D. B. (2011). The dynamics of Green HRM behaviors: A cognitive social information processing approach. *German Journal of Human Resource Management*, 25(2), 117- 139.